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Career Choice in Early Childhood Care and Education: A Socio-Philosophical Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Decisions on career choice have critical implications for the survival of the individual and the national development of states and this accounts for why the extent in which a state handles issues that border on career choice determine its degree of responsibility and responsiveness to the people. Using philosophical research methodology and constructivism as theoretical framework, this study discuss the importance of career choice in early childhood care and education especially for a state like Nigeria that is desirous of real human capital and national development. The study identifies reasons for and against career choice in early childhood care and education particularly in Nigeria and goes further to suggest practical measures which range from offering scholarships, bursaries, luring best candidates into choosing their careers in early childhood care and education, providing the right teacher learning environment and offering automatic employment to candidates who choose their career in early childhood care and education as possible road maps that can trigger epical and phenomenal interest in Nigerians to choose careers on early childhood care and education.

Keywords: Career choice, early childhood care and education, Nigeria, socio-philosophical analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Across the globe, one desire that is a focal flash point of every rational and responsible person is to live a fulfilled and impactful life where one can at least relatively satisfy most of his basic needs on his own without depending on parents, friends or welfare schemes and welfare provisions from the state in the case of citizens who come from states where welfare schemes and welfare provisions for citizens who cannot provide themselves are part of the cardinal national policy of the state. Any leadership structure of a state that has established and stabilized the social, political, economic and cultural environment of the state where citizens who have come of age provide for themselves can be said to have laid sustainable foundations for fast tracking and promoting the maturity and independence of her citizens, which on its own can be taken as a demonstration of a sense of responsibility both on the part of the individual and on the part of the state.

This, when achieved can be said to be a sound philosophy upon which a people and their state can be built and correspondingly a prayer and action point of every responsible citizen and every responsible leader as well as a focus and policy direction that all the organs and instruments of the state should be driven towards. States and leaders in such states make and encourage their citizens to live productive, fulfilled and impactful lives when states and leaders in such states engineer or lay foundations that can trigger

reforms and positive revolutions where citizens especially in their youthful and early adult ages are meaningfully, existentially, pragmatically and functionally engaged and youths and adults have fulfilled and impactful lives when they choose a career that sustainably and meaningfully provide them work and income capable of putting food on their table and equally taking care of their needs all through their life. In the journey into youth and adulthood, most responsible youths and adults make lifelong critical decision on the type of career (career choice) that they can engage in and through that career make a living that is capable of helping them realize and achieve their dreams in life. In fact, career choice is a focal flashpoint and a centre of action in which the day to day thinking and actions of any responsible person revolves and by extension the centre of all the deliberations of the state when focus and attention is on empowerment, liberation and emancipation of the people. In short, the career one chooses in one's journey of life is so determinant and critical so much that one's success and one's failure in life can be one hundred percent dependent on the choice of career one makes and it is also true that the stability of the national economy and national development of states are heavily dependent on the relationships that exist between the career choice of the citizens and the economy of the state. Economies of states that are heavily dependent on skills and careers of foreign nationals may likely suffer because the expertise for the survival of the economy lies in the land of foreign citizens who are not citizens of the state and this in all honesty constitutes security threats, political and economic sabotage to the social, economic and political development of the state and its people. These are reasons why the ability of a state and its leaders to create enabling environments that can promote and support citizens in their drives and aspirations to identify the career of their citizens and support their citizens to legitimately pursue such careers are indexes for assessing how responsible, caring and accountable a state and its leaders can be to their people.

Most states and most persons across the globe are aware of this and have exclusively devoted so much time and so much attention to determining and influencing the career trajectories of their people. In fact, how serious career choice or choice of career of the individual in the state or society ranks among other choices the individual makes can be attested to by the fact that parents who are already in some careers and who have seen the prospects or otherwise of some careers, guide, discuss, influence and suggest to their sons, daughters and wards the need for proper scrutiny, analysis and proper knowledge of any career choice they make and in the same way, responsible states encourage their citizens to make career choices that robustly align with the critical sectors of the economy and critical infrastructure of the state so as to protect the interests of the state as well as safeguard national interests and national security of the state; failure of which may amount to exposing the secrets and weaknesses of the state.

The above points in the direction that the choice of career or career choice any individual settles for or chooses must naturally be influenced by some values which may derive or owe their roots to internal (intrinsic) or external (extrinsic) factors and these all together may target providing an individual a sense of personal fulfillment, a sense of rendering a critical service to humanity or expanding and partaking in co-creation with God-Almighty. It is correct and has to be pointed out loud and clear that the choice of career or career choice an individual makes has a lot to say about the individual especially the individual's commitment to issues that affect humanity and the individual's personality. In other words, the involvement of an individual in one career or the other is usually an entry point for judging and assessing the personality, value system, worth, like and dislike of the individual in the society.

All over the world, people choose education and teaching as one career choice destination where they can easily be impactful to society and to humanity. These educationists or teachers who choose education, teaching or supply human capital development or human capacity building have at the back of their mind the actualization of any of the following: the desire for personal fulfillment, the desire to render a critical service to humanity and most importantly the desire to partake in co-creation with God-Almighty. In fact, any critical observer can quickly notice that true human capital development, human capacity building or conscious transformation of people from lower and primitive state to a higher and civilized one is at the heart of education and teaching and that the tier of education and teaching that is the foundation for

achieving what is expected of all the other tiers of education and by extension the national dreams of a state is at the early childhood care and education level.

The above exposition simply points in the direction that there is a relationship between career choice and national development of states and it is also a fact that the quality of investments in human capital development and human capacity building predicts and determines the national development of states. These facts in all honestly make career choice in human capital development and human capacity building especially at the early childhood care and education level a subject matter in which adequate attention must be paid to. The justification for this phenomenal attention to this level of education is deep rooted in the fact that development in a state, which investment in man triggers is comparable to a building where the better the investment that is made at the foundation levels of the building, the better the entire structure. All these simply highlight the importance of early childhood care and education as a foundational and fundamental level of education and human capital development which deserve special attention, (Nwaokugha & Agbarakwe, 2024). As sound as this can be, a worrisome trend and a cause for concern is that despite the fact that genuine national development hinges on human beings and the right point in which the right investments and the right foundations can be made in human beings are at the early childhood care and education level, many persons neglect and cast aspersion at choosing their careers at this level of education and government particularly in Nigeria has not done much to change this trend.

This study is specifically focused on career choice in early childhood care and education and the major objectives are to highlight the importance of early childhood and education in the national development of states, to undertake a socio-philosophical analysis of career choice in early childhood care and education where focus can be on the attitudinal dispositions of the members of the society towards making career choice in early childhood and education and to make a case on the need for individuals who have the right mental and behavioural dispositions to make or choose their careers in early childhood care and education for the sustainable growth and development of humanity. In other words, this paper is focused on creating awareness on career choice especially in early childhood care and education with a view to highlighting why it is necessary for citizens who are genuinely interested in the national development of their states in particular and humanity in general to take up careers in early childhood care and education. The study will on the other hand identify reasons why citizens in Nigeria and some other states are lackadaisical, hesitant and reluctant to take up careers in early childhood care and education.

As there is almost no body of coherent research on career choice motivation in early childhood care and education, (Weiss, Syring, Keller-Schneider, Hellstein & Kiel, 2018:500), this study can be significant in a number of ways: the study can identify motives why people choose or do not choose careers in early childhood care and education and more importantly, the study can serve as a guide or sign- post for guiding stakeholders and policy makers on the right steps to take so as to adequately explore opportunities for national development that abound in early childhood care and education, the study will also contribute to the growth of knowledge across the world especially in the discipline of early childhood care and education by engineering radical and revolutionary transformations whose pedagogical, ideological and philosophical explorations can qualitatively contribute to resolving inherent issues in early childhood care and education, advocate and make strong case for quality improvements in early childhood care and education particularly on issues bordering on recruitment and career choice in early childhood care and education. The study will highlight potential benefits the Nigerian state and by extension humanity generally can derive when the right calibre of persons make their career in early childhood care and education.

Lastly the study will highlight reasons why Nigerians are reluctant, lackadaisical and hesitant in taking up careers in early childhood care and education and more importantly the study will guide and lay foundations for formulating and implementing policies for improving education generally and early childhood care and education in particular in Nigeria and beyond.

The theoretical framework upon which this study is based on is social constructivism. As a theory of knowledge construction, social constructivism holds human beings to be the architect, builder and constructor of whatever knowledge that exists. In other words, this theory of knowledge construction establishes that human beings through their daily interactions and daily experiences with their fellow human beings and the environment generate, establish and construct knowledge. One revelation that is associated with social constructivism is that as a theory of knowledge construction, it subscribes to the idea that no knowledge is ready made and kept or preserved in a market or warehouse, rather knowledge generation, production and construction is a product of man's conscious endeavor and engagement where creativity and critical thinking and critical consciousness are fundamental and foundational entry points. That creativity, critical thinking and critical consciousness are key in constructivism aligns or identifies it as a basic component of qualitative research design and its alignment and identification with qualitative research design according to Nwaokugha and Abiakwu (2024:167) make it a destination of choice in the hands of scholars and researchers who are desirous of breaking new frontiers of knowledge, who are committed to solving and resolving general epistemological, metaphysical and axiological issues in the affairs of man and his society, who show receptive and robust enthusiasm to explore and respond to the demands of change in the world of knowledge in particular and the society at large and constructivism is supportive of collaboration among scholars and researchers, in addition to the expansion of the frontiers of knowledge.

The beauty and appropriateness of this theory of knowledge construction for this study lies in its ability to instill or harp it into the consciousness of learners, researchers and that man is at the centre of knowledge production and the study correspondingly targets scholars creating the right awareness and insights that human beings create knowledge and honesty and sincerely demands attitudinal and behavioural dispositions where according to Nwaokugha and Abiakwu (2024:62), every learner or stakeholder in the knowledge industry must endeavor to expand the frontiers of knowledge and must demonstrate a sense of active participation and active engagement in knowledge production. It follows that by this disposition, constructivism as a theory of knowledge construction makes a case for ethical obligations from all stakeholders in the knowledge industry to make it a point of duty to keep the light of the knowledge industry alive by prioritizing the continuous generation, building and construction of knowledge.

Methodologically, this study adopts the qualitative, which is also called the philosophical research approach. The modus operandi of a qualitative or philosophical research includes what Angadi (2019:37) calls "the collection of extensive narrative data on many variables over an extended period in a naturalistic setting to gain insights not possible using other types of research methods. In their own contributions on the robustness, richness and receptivity of qualitative or philosophical research methodology, Ishtiaq and Naz (2024:10) write that:

Qualitative (philosophical) research is often exploratory aiming to uncover new insights, perspectives and understanding within educational setting. Qualitative research in education involves collecting and analyzing non-numeral data such as interviews, observations, case studies and document analysis. The aim is to generate in-depth insights, explore meanings and understand the underlying processes that shape educational phenomena.

The above features of qualitative or philosophical research methodology align with the position of Merriam and Tisdell (2015), who write that qualitative or philosophical research methodology offers scholars and researchers a comprehensive, inclusive and in-depth opportunity to bring to bear in any particular study the individual experiences, perceptions and insights of a researcher or a scholar. This is because qualitative or philosophical research design according to Creswell (2015) provides scholars and researchers guides, insights and foundations for fundamentally resorting to investigative processes where such researchers and scholars can deploy systematic, logical analysis and interpretation of phenomena by

rationally, critically, reflectively and creatively examining, comparing, contrasting, and categorizing the subject matter or topic that is the focus of a study. The robust and receptive space which qualitative or philosophical research methodology offers scholars and researchers can be so because qualitative or philosophical research according to Nwaokugha and Danladi (2016) incorporates speculation, analysis and prescription.

Speculation as a method of philosophical research makes waves in the pursuit of knowledge across disciplines and part of what is responsible for this is that speculation constantly reinvents itself (Nwaokugha & Nwaogu, 2024:63) and speculation cuts across disciplinary epistemological territories as it can be applied in philosophy and its applied disciplines, social sciences and the natural science (Nwaokugha & Agbarakwe, 2024:253).

Exploring the multiple layers in which speculation can apply, Swedberg (2021:46) identifies two basic meaning that can be associated with speculation when he writes that speculation “refers to risky but potentially very profitable economic activity and it refers to making of conjectures without firm evidence”; suggesting that the meaning and use of the term in one context may not be its meaning in the other context. In this study, we shall limit ourselves to the second meaning as identified by Swedberg (2021) and even at that, different scholars and researchers define speculation in their own idiosyncratic ways.

Haung, Xie and Chen (2021) write that speculation or speculative thinking refers to thinking about past and future possibilities which includes counterfactual thinking, prefectual thinking and other types of thinking. According to Aminigo (1999) and Agulanna (2011), speculation or speculative thinking refers to attempt to find logical coherence in an entire realm of thought while Oduor (2010:97), writes that speculation or speculative thinking invokes a meaning that revolves around man’s conscious ability “to wonder, conjecture, guess or to hypothesize”. Inherent in speculation or speculative thinking as a method of philosophical or qualitative research is its ability to engineering revolutionary and superlative reforms, transforming innovation, critical and creative thinking that can lay foundations for improved actions and super performances in the future. This can be the basis upon which Taggart (2012) writes that speculation or speculative thinking provides man and his institution a kind of philosophy of actions that shapes and influences public philosophy on one hand and philosophy of life of individual on the other, developments that in all ramifications serve as provocateur for actions.

By way of simple analytic reflection, it can be correct to say that speculation or speculative thinking opens new window of opportunities for new alternative lens of enquiry or new lens of looking at situation that creatively, receptively and critically challenges man and his institutions into reconceiving, reforming, rethinking and transforming themselves into something nobler than what used to be the case in the past. The truth of the above can be established when viewed along the mantra that man speculates in other to know more especially when faced with realities that are ultimately unknown to him. Because of this, there are disciplines and topics that are more receptive to speculation and speculative thinking and such include topics and disciplines that have their roots in metaphysics and axiology. Axiological and metaphysical topics are receptive to speculation and speculative thinking simply because issues they preoccupy themselves with do not easily yield themselves to a one-size-fit-all interpretation, meaning that such topics and issues shift their epistemological boundaries as they consistently take into cognizance the phenomenon of change, where practitioners respond to circumstances based on the prevailing evidence at the moment and are ready to change in the future base on the prevailing circumstance at the time.

Speculation or speculative thinking works in a research or study when a researcher or scholar logically, coherently and systematically builds up ideas and shows how one ideas is inherently linked to other ideas in the whole system of ideas. Many scholars and researchers highlight this inherent feature of speculation in different ways. According to Nwaokugha and Wogonwu (2023:4), speculation as a method of philosophical research is deep rooted in a “sense of logical unity, logical coherence and logical clarity about a presentation that is the subject matter of philosophical discourse” and Nwaokugha and Danladi (2016:421) highlight same point when they write that “the foundation of this method of enquiry is that the

soundness or reasonableness of any proposition can be established through its rootedness in the science of logic or the various orderly sequences that lead to a conclusion". What is at the heart of any meaningful and effective speculation is the fact that there must be a relationship between a conclusion and its premise. Effective use of logic and language in presenting and communicating ideas play critical and crucial roles in speculation and speculative thinking.

Analysis as a method used in carrying out philosophical researches exclusively focuses on revealing or making explicit whatsoever meaning that may be associated with words, terms, concepts and prepositions. Analysis is done through the analyst's indulgence in critical examination of words, terms and concepts and by so doing whatever ambiguities, contradictions and absurdities that may be associated with such words, terms and concepts may be identified and the particular meaning of the word, term or concept that is the focus of the philosophical discourse can be focused on. In fact, Nwaokugha and Danladi (2016:421) say it all when they write that researchers and scholars who use the analytic method start by breaking down their "subject matter into smaller unit that constitute it and at the same time show how all are related in attaining a specific objective".

It is imperative we say and say it authoritatively that analysis is principally undertaken in philosophical studies to ensure precision and clarity and through this way avoid ambiguity in the meaning that the analyst intends to make his focal flashpoint. This is instructive because analysts are aware that most crisis, misunderstandings, conflicts and disagreements that have stained relationships including retrogressing man and his institutions are principally caused by faulty use of words, terms and concepts or miscommunication and misunderstanding of ideas. This revelation therefore points in the direction that analysts in their business of analysis target resolving conflict, promoting collaboration, building peace and promoting harmonious and cooperative living, developments that come to fruition through phenomenal and epical minimization of the occurrence of crises, conflicts, disagreements and misunderstandings in the day to day affairs of man and his institution. In fact, this semantic clarity and peace building culture that is inherent in analysis is spotlighted by Nwaokugha (2021:160) when he writes that:

The advantage of analysis is that through it, meanings are clarified and ambiguities are resolves and this clarification and resolution of ambiguities helps members of the society to amicably address, resolve and bring to the barest minimum the occurrence of conflicts, misunderstanding disagreements, violent confrontations and instability-inducing behaviours that make peace elusive by threatening harmonious co-existence and progressive development of the society.

Analysis is of two major types namely conceptual analysis and linguistic analysis. Conceptual analysis focusses on establishing if the meaning that is ascribed or associated to a concept actually represents what that concept stands for while linguistic analysis focuses on establishing if the meaning ascribed or associated to a sentence actually represents what the sentence semantically stands for.

Prescription, when used as a methodology for carrying out philosophical research is any logical, coherent, conscious and systematic attempts to establish standards for judging values or establishing criteria for making prescriptive value judgment. What has been stated above has been amplified by some scholars who discuss and present prescription as a philosophical research methodology in language that everyone can understand namely "to prescribe is to recommend or set down as rule or guide" (Oduor, 2010). What the above simply reveals is that the suggestions and recommendations which any well undertaken study must incorporate fall within the frame of reference of prescription (Nwaokugha: 2021:102). In fact, the overriding importance of prescription in any serious academic study is highlighted by Nwaokugha and Nwaogu (2024:64) when they write that "Prescription is at the heart of every research as every research targets solving or resolving one problem or the other and concrete and identifiable lines of action for solving and resolving such identified problem are what prescription focusses attention on".

True, prescription is at the heart of every study, but scholars whose areas of specialization are axiology-aesthetics, political philosophy, social philosophy and ethics cannot effectively perform or deliver their statutory responsibilities to the society without indulging or embracing prescription and the reason for this revolves around the phenomenon of change, which consistently dictates the rhythm of the action of man, including what can be done in the future. This suggests that the pattern of change in any society or in human affairs is the sole determinant or influencer of what any committed and devoted scholar prescribes, a development that points in the direction that no prescription is ready-made and correspondingly there should always be space where the right epistemological and attitudinal dispositions expected of every scholar can be one where scholars step up their games especially in their area of specialization in anticipation or readiness for addressing, resolving and responding to issues and challenges in their various fields.

The importance of the philosophical research methodology for this study lies in the optimistic note made by Nwoke and Nwaokugha (2024), who write that every branch of knowledge benefits from the rigorous inquiry and philosophical reflections that are associated with the qualitative and philosophical research methodology. To this end, qualitative or philosophical research methodology is credited with empowering scholars and researchers with skills that can enable them to engineer epistemological revolutions that can result in research investigations that are phenomenal ground breaking breakthroughs, achievements, which occur through the development of phenomenal abilities that skyrocket the curiosity of researchers and scholars to venture into academic investigations that target breaking new frontiers of knowledge, which ordinarily would have remained unimaginable. This points in the direction that qualitative or philosophical research methodology is synonymous with stimulating in scholars and researchers the zeal to continuously try out new options for addressing and resolving issues in the society, no wonder the qualitative or philosophical research methodology has become the trending destination of choice among scholars and researchers.

What has become the tradition and norm for studies that employ the qualitative or philosophical research methodology is for researchers to create sufficient awareness, robust insights or pay in-depth attention to key concepts and terms that are the focus of their study and to this, we now turn.

Early Childhood Care and Education

Across developed, developing and underdeveloped states, there is an upsurge in the demand for education and there is equally a phenomenal willingness to provide it. The upsurge in the demand for education and a corresponding willingness to provide it has made education a social good and a social provision that is at the centre of politics and a social provision in which there is epical and monumental policy summersaults. In the various politics, political intrigues and policy summersault in which education is at the center, there is the recognition that investments in human capacity development and human capacity building are the best investments any state can make for its national development and guided by this mindset, there is what Nwaokugha and Smith-Ogizeh (2025:155) call

Growing awareness to deepen the provision of education so much that it becomes more inclusive and comprehensive so that no layer of the society is left behind and without access to education and this human capital development insight and revolution has expanded the education space so much that presently there are epical and phenomenal interest to consciously extend and expand the educational provision to citizens in their early stages of life.

Providing care and rudimentary learning experiences to citizens in their earliest stage of life is called early childhood care and education. Early childhood care and education is a segment of educational provision which individuals, nations, and international organizations have in recent times devoted excess attention to and what has resulted out of this is a plethora of individual declaration on how to explore the numerous advantages that come with it. One common denominator that is common to all such declaration is that early childhood care and education is care, learning or rudimentary educational experiences that are

provided to learners prior to their official admission into the primary school. Within this period, two things take place namely care and education in a manner where one comes before the other. Care comes before education and scholars discuss care and education from different angles. According to Nwaokugha (2016:214), care is “the surveillance of the adult over younger ones or the infant for the purpose of giving and providing him/her protection, security and keeping him or her away or safe from danger. Ridza, Ahmad and Vadeveloo (2024:72) agree with the above when they write that childcare institutions primarily cater to the children’s survival and protection while parents are working” and all these may account for why Hayes (2007) writes that care is custodial in tone.

Education in the context of early childhood care and education refers to all preschool activities, which focusses on care and learning in a kind of formalized teaching and learning in a school-like setting (Urban, 2009), that targets preparing children for primary school and beyond (Ridza et al 2024). A more elaborate and detailed discussion of education in early childhood care and education discourse is provided by Nwaokugha and Nwaogu (2024:66), when they write that education in early childhood care and education focuses;

On developing higher order activity or creative and critical thinking skills that target promoting continuous learning in the younger ones especially aspect of rudimentary learning that can stimulate in the learners the ability to respond to challenges they find in environments in which they find themselves.

It can be correct to say that care and education can be transitional trajectories that kick off from the birth of an individual, travel on the same road but maintain different speed, rhythm, depth, (Nwaokugha, 2016) and more importantly do not target the same axiological and epistemological destinations. In keeping with its different axiological and epistemological destinations, different states have their different conceptions of early childhood care and education, meaning that early childhood care and education is structurally flexible so much that states have autonomous control over how they structure and provide it to their citizens. This is evident in the fact that there are states that peg their early childhood and education at 0-5 years (Federal Republic of Nigeria, (2004) 0-8 years (UNESCO, 2017), Kim, Brand & Zelter, 2024) and from 0-9 years (Kuhne & Fakie, 2019), respectively suggesting that no two states can consciously have a uniform early childhood care and education system. Stakeholder and policy makers in states that prioritize early childhood care and education and its provision therefore target using that tier of education to enhance the moral, social, cognitive, emotional, linguistic, hygienic, physical and psychological development of the child that can be supportive of engineering a smooth transition that can facilitate and enhance learning from preschool environment to the formal school system. A broader justification for the global commitment towards early childhood care and education (Parveen, 2024) is highlighted by Nwaokugha and Agbarakwe (2024:257) when they write that:

Early childhood care and education incorporates social welfare programmes and policies which at first target the betterment of the infant or the young in the state and by implication is a social justice mechanism for progressively rewriting the developmental trajectories or narratives of the state and humanity in general.

The Concept of Career and Career Choice

The concept of career invokes a meaning that revolves around a profession or occupation that is consciously chosen by an individual as a route for lifelong creative activity or work through which the individual can earn a living. In other words, it is a conglomerate of professional and occupational activity an individual indulges in that provides him opportunities for work all through the life of the individual or all through the period the individual is in a good health condition. Careers that are worth the name require some intellectual cognition, a diligent commitment to acquiring such intellectual cognition and a fairly

long period of time for mastering all what it takes to practice or to offer services to members of the society. Some careers attract some levels of social prestige to themselves and on the basis of this, such careers are money spinners as they enhance the economic fortunes of those who practice them, in addition to making them earn a lot of respect from the members of the public. The combined power of social prestige, enhanced economic fortunes and respect from members of the public make such careers a destination of choice for many people in the society. People who earn their living in or through careers where the above are prevalent exert so much influence over the members of the society so much that they as well as their careers serve as role models for the members of the society, a development that makes members of the society to opt for or choose such a career.

The above is revealing and part of what it reveals is that there are determinant motivations for the different career choices which people make and on the basis of this, there are different schools of thought that influence or determine career choice. Arriving at this moment and resolving issues that accompany it is one herculean task in one's history. A truth that is as old as man is that people face critical reflective moments when it comes to deciding what career choice to make and what makes it so is that career choice is linked to the future or is a conscious plan for tomorrow so much that what people become tomorrow is one hundred percent dependent on the career choice decisions that people make today and under this critical and tensed moment, most people are guided principally by their individual preferences, areas they have superlative innate abilities, the profession of their role models and the professions that have brought about epical and phenomenal emancipation, liberation and empowerment in terms of wealth and popularity to people. There are some persons who opt or choose some careers due to the critical nature of such careers to the effective and efficient functioning of man and the society and some people choose careers that take them closer to participating and partaking in co-creation with God-Almighty. The work of teachers especially those teachers who work in early childhood care and education institutions are in close alignment with co-creation with God.

Apart from the above, Borchert (2002) writes that environment, personality and opportunity are important areas that affect the career choice of people. Environment influences the career choice of an individual either positively or negatively and this is in the form of the environment influencing and determining the choice, attachment and embrace of a career by someone. Put slightly different, the prevalence of certain developments in any environment one finds himself can cause one to identify with a particular career in life. Personality comes in to determine and influence an individual's career choice or choice of a career when an individual possesses traits and charisma that stands out as basic qualities that anyone aspiring to practice so and so profession or occupation must have. Here, the innate and inherent alignment of the behavioural traits of an individual is an important determinant of the choice of career of an individual hence people who make intelligent and wise career plans are those that are self-motivated to identify with a particular career out of choice, self-conviction and the possession of identifiable traits that align with a particular career or occupation. Opportunity as a factor that determines the choice of career or career choice of an individual is futuristic in outlook in terms of possible prospects that a particular career can hold for those who identify with it. What comes to mind here are the chances of one who has identified with one career or the other having the prospect of securing jobs or gainful employment that can banish poverty in one's life.

Success in anyone's chosen career can be measured or determined by the degree of opportunities for upward mobility and the measure of stability that such a career can afford the individual and the society and this accounts for why efforts are intensified to create awareness about occupation, vocation or world of work and through this way sensitize and conscientize people to fit in after making their choices. All over the world, people choose education and teaching as one career choice destination where people render critical service to humanity. These educationists or teachers who choose education, teaching or simply human capital development or human capacity building especially at the early childhood care and education level have at the back of their minds the actualization of any of the following: the desire for

personal fulfilment, the desire to render a critical service to humanity and most importantly the desire to partake in co-creation with God-Almighty.

In fact, it is a fact that cannot be disputed that taking up a career in early childhood care and education aligns with many foundational and fundamental requirements for national development and sustainable future for humanity and correspondingly the best career choice anyone can make. There are however on the other side people who regard taking up career in early childhood care and education as the most debasing and demeaning career choice anyone can make. On the basis of the dual reactions, the next section of this study shall focus on socio-philosophical analysis of career choice in early childhood care and education in Nigeria.

Socio-philosophical Analysis of Career Choice in Early Childhood Care and Education in Nigeria.

Taking up a career in teaching is one of those human activities that is phenomenally charged with emotions so much that such emotions are expressed by the practitioners in the teaching profession on one hand and those who are not practitioners in the teaching profession on the other. This unique feature of teaching makes it a human activity that is constantly under the critical watch, critical scrutiny and critical surveillance of the members of the society especially when decisions that border on choice of career are about to be made. In fact, discussions that border on teaching usually stimulate behavioural dispositions that constantly tilt towards critical assessment and evaluation from the general public, which on its own conditions practitioners and those who are not practitioners into coming up with some kind of generalizations about the prospects of career choice in teaching especially at the early childhood care and education level.

One obvious development that confronts those that wish to choose or that have chosen teaching as a career especially at the early childhood care and education level is a split among practitioner and in this split, there are those who see choice of career or career choice at the early childhood care and education level as a road to nowhere and correspondingly a consciously made choice towards retrogression as career choice in that level of education is synonymous with powerlessness and poverty. On the other hand, there are practitioners who see their choice of career or career choice at the early childhood care and education level as a consciously chosen road map for their self-fulfillment and self-actualization as it affords them opportunities for helping children and young people become capable and responsible adults (Ornstein & Levine, 2004), who can creatively, constructively and meaningfully contribute to the development of their state in particular and humanity generally. The split into those who see career choice or choice of career in early childhood care and education as a roadmap to poverty and powerlessness and equally a roadmap to self-fulfillment and self-actualization especially its potentials to help children and young children become capable and responsible adults and correspondingly a foundation and pillar for human capital development of our society.

Many persons are hesitant and lackadaisical when it comes to career choice in early childhood care and education and these persons who are hesitant and lackadaisical when it comes to career choice in early childhood care and education do so on the ground that members of the society epically and phenomenally under-appreciate, neglect and disrespect members of the early childhood care and education workforce, in addition to overlooking them in matters that border on wages, benefits and welfare. Part of the reason why people who choose their career in early childhood care and education and teachers in early childhood care and education institutions are not cared for, respected and recognized is the fact that the greater number of the members of the workforce in early childhood care and education institutions are women. In most countries, women are viewed as second class citizens and correspondingly taken as class of people who must not be treated fairly or who must be denied of their rightful entitlements. This perception about women is extended to everything women are involved in, particularly in the early childhood care and education sector, where the society compounds their woes and predicaments by seeing their roles in the early childhood care and education set up as merely those of low-skilled workers, baby sitters and

caretakers, a vocation and service anyone can undertake without any training or formal education. The categorization of everyone who has chosen a career in early childhood care and education as a low-skilled worker, a baby sitter and a caretaker has disastrous consequences and part of it is that such generalization helps to force those who are qualified out of early childhood care and education institutions from providing high quality and superlative developmentally appropriate education (Mahadewi, 2024:3) to learners at this transformative and intervention level of education.

Again, this attitude towards women in early childhood care and education institutions is greeted with a reward system where those who choose their careers in early childhood care and education “earn wage below the legally stipulated minimum wage” (Economic Policy Institute, 2020) and consequently are condemned to endure poverty and hardship if they continue to remain in early childhood care and education institutions all through their lives. To resist poverty and hardship is to resign from early childhood care and education institutions and to continuously be applying for jobs even when one has one and this has its own implications for achieving the core mandate of early childhood care and education.

According to Kim et al (2024) “frequent changes of teachers can disrupt children’s routines and relationships, leading to potential negative impacts on their development”. For sure, neglect, lack of recognition and respect, low pay and lack of social benefits for those who have chosen early childhood care and education as a career choice leave impressions in the psyche of the people and this extends in the manner in which they show and demonstrate commitment to duty, in the way they perform and in the way they take proper charge and adequate care of the learners who are under their custody.

Scholars and institutions have taken cognizance of the too many negative developments in early childhood care and education institutions across the globe. Kim et al (2024) draw attention to the global general neglect which persons who choose their career in early childhood care and education face when they write that such issues as low wages, lack of benefits and high turnover rates are significant factors that impact on the professional lives of persons whose career choice are in early childhood care and education. It is not to be doubted that people whose career choice condemn them to work in establishments where they do not enjoy any recognition or support are much more likely to suffer burn out, which according to Kim et al (2024) “Primarily arises from the demanding nature of their roles, often exacerbated by a lack of adequate support and resources”. To be added to the demanding nature of early childhood care and education are inherent features in early childhood care and education itself. Early childhood care and education is fundamentally fragmented and multifaceted to the extent of encompassing preschool teachers, preschool child care providers, family and child providers, centre based providers and head-start and such fragmentation and multifaceted nature of early childhood care and education hardly makes each practitioner a sound professional in any area of education. The fact that one is fragmentally educated without an identifiable area of expertise or specialization can be emotionally challenging and intellectually disturbing. What this reveals is that the possibility or the naturalness of one gaining some level of expertise or specialization out of accumulated years of experience that one ought to gain from one’s place of work is limited in the case of those whose careers are in early childhood care and education.

This development produces psychological trauma and instability in those who choose their careers in early childhood care and education and this is part of why stress, burnout and other forms of trauma and psychological instability are common features among those who choose their careers in early childhood care and education. We can say and say it very strongly that the prevalence of stress and burnout among those who choose their careers in early childhood care and education is also linked to the people’s poor condition of service, lack of benefits, lack of developmental prospects as well as the various backgrounds of the various learners who need dissimilar and un-identical developmental needs. Stress and psychological issues increase and multiply for those who choose their careers in early childhood care and education due to the poor state of infrastructure of most of such schools especially in those states where educational provisions at this level is the exclusive rights of the private sector to provide and this is compounded by the excessive demands on teacher from the owners of such schools to make up or

improvise including urging the teachers to promote and initiate curricular and pedagogical innovations that are supportive of fostering, promoting and enhancing learning environments that can be inclusive and beneficial to all learners. In the face of all these, one variable is constant namely those who choose their career in early childhood care and education experience terrible and devastating devaluation in the form of going through experiences which Kim et al (2024) describe as limited autonomy in the job, experience insufficient collegial support as well as face challenges of managing difficult behaviour, development that leads to emotional exhaustion and a sense of detachment from work. Part of what may be responsible for the above may hinge on conflicting interests among diverse governing bodies (Udanyanga, 2024), especially as early childhood care and education in most developing and underdeveloped states are managed and controlled by private investors whose sole interest for investing in early childhood care and education is profit maximization as against the pursuit of the ideals and visions of the state.

There are on the other hand people whose motivation for choosing their careers in early childhood care and education are borne out of their genuine commitments to laying foundation for human capital development and more importantly participating in co-creation with God and these people take into cognizance the various roles of early childhood care and education as having such positive ability to function as a transformative force for social change and social reengineering as a critical intervention strategy for addressing issues of poverty and inequality, a new policy and investment destination and direction that focuses on getting the children on the right track and by extension fixing the developmental dreams and aspirations of states, a dynamic measure for making equality and social justice a norm in the state, a durable and progressive dynamic for increasing and expanding access to education and more importantly getting the young ones set and prepared for the challenges and rigours of learning at the primary school level.

It is not to be doubted that across the globe, there are people who demonstrate genuine love for younger ones and show exceptional interests by going extra miles in empowering progressive actions that target improving their condition or working with them especially to help them actualize their potentials as well as those who have patriotic and nationalistic zeal and such people have convinced themselves that states which make waves and dominate in scientific, technological, political, economic, social, entrepreneurial and managerial breakthroughs are those states that recognize the fact that sound academic foundations for learners, the cultivation of the right intellectual spirit and conscious investments in learners at a very early stage in the life of the younger ones has no substitutes in raising and triggering the interests, enthusiasm and curiosity of the younger ones for educational pursuits and correspondingly through such intervention consciously raise a generation of people whose commitments to achieving and realizing national dreams and national developments can be epic and phenomenal. Those who have this forward looking and visionary mindset see the end from the beginning and at the same time recognize the centrality of sound foundations and genuine investments in the younger ones as pillars and foundations upon which any state can realize its developmental aspirations, a major departure from the past and consequently a transformative, radical and revolutionary motivation why some persons make their career choice in early childhood care and education.

The ability and interest to work with children and establish harmonious, robust and cordial relationships with children especially the desire and inclination to positively reform and influence people at their younger age, helping people to cultivate, develop, generate and document ideas for posterity is one serious reason why people opt for careers in early childhood care and education. These people who opt for careers in early childhood care and education subscribe to the mantra of catch them young, in addition to equating the human system to building infrastructure, where the basic epistemological, metaphysical and axiological belief is that the better the foundation, the better the structure. Guided by this, these people are strongly convinced that care and education for the young ones are the best investments that can radically and revolutionally reposition a state and citizens of a state that are generally committed to developing their states.

One truth that is constant in developed, developing and under developed states is the recognition that children are valuable assets (Ridza, et al, 2024) and relating with them especially teaching them and through this way make quality contributions that can trigger their ability to realize and actualize themselves helps to produce a sense of fulfilment and a sense of satisfaction in the teacher as the efforts of the teacher in developing the learner is the foundation upon which the desire for the development of human capital development and the national development of the state depends. To this end, the motive upon which some people choose careers in teaching generally and early childhood care and education in particular according to Ornstein and Levine (2006) include (1) Love of children (2) desire to impart knowledge (3) interest in and excitement about teaching, and (4) desire to perform a valuable service to humanity.

It is also important we point out that people can make career choice in early childhood care and education just for the purposes of becoming role models to younger learners and their parents especially in societies and ethnic groups where the people suffer inferiority complex, various forms of injustice, deprivation and marginalization. The presence of such people who have chosen their careers in early childhood care and education can help to build confidence and trust that can positively and potentially change the narratives for the better for such people who suffer from inferiority complex, various forms of justice, deprivation and marginalization.

A more serious reason why people can choose their career in early childhood care and education is the development and demonstration of a sense of care, devotion and commitment to upholding respect for human rights, pursuit of social justice and other concepts whose philosophical underpinnings make case for powerless people such as young ones who do not have any one to make their case. To this end, choosing a career in early childhood care and education can be said to be a response to divine command especially that recorded in the bible book of Proverbs chapter 31 vs 8-9 which says; speak up for those who cannot speak for themselves, for the rights of all who are destitute, speak up and judge fairly, defend the rights of the poor and needy". Equally the bible book of Job chapter 26 verse 2-3 speaks and holds such people who choose their career in early childhood care and education in great honour when it writes that:

How you have helped the powerless! How you have saved the arm that is feeble! What advice you have offered to one without wisdom! And what great insight you have displayed. The above quotations simply point hand to the co-creation role and responsibility with God that serves as a force that attracts people to make their careers in early childhood care and education.

CONCLUSION

Taking decisions that lead one into the choice of a career upon which one earns a living is one of the critical moments in the life of an individual and what seems to account for the critical and tensed moment in the lives of individuals who are about to make career choice is that different motivations determine and influence different people in their choice of career and these difference motivations determine and shape the commitment, attitude, success and failure of such individuals in their chosen careers. Individuals are not the only people who show concern in issues of career choice, responsible states build-in career and career choice decisions for their citizens in their day to day deliberations about the governance of the state and why this is a priority is that one index for assessing the degree of responsibility and responsiveness of any state is the extent in which the state comes up with creative, lucrative and practical policies that can stimulate the effective tapping, exploration and galvanization of the various skills and talents of the citizens of the state into career options for the good of the citizens and the state. This directly means that the career choice of citizens of a state can be an index for predicting the line of progress and development of a people and their state.

This study has specifically focused on career choice in early childhood care and education in Nigeria and reasons why some people may dislike career choice in early childhood care and education as well as reasons why many people may choose their career in early childhood care and education have been

identified. In all these, any state that is desirous of solid investments and development in the future with the hope of keying into the philosophy of sustainable development must prioritize investments in its younger ones and correspond same with raising a standard workforce or an ambitious army of career personnel who can cater for the needs of such younger ones whose responsibility it is to translate the ideas, wishes and aspirations of the adult population into reality. This can be socio-philosophically guided by the fact the state and its functioning can be compared to an architectural structure where the better the foundation, the better the entire structure, implying that the earlier a state makes investments in her younger ones and provides incentive targeted at convincing her citizens to take up careers in early childhood care and education, the better the chances and prospects of that state in terms of meeting its human capital needs and developmental objectives.

This means that states that are desirous of genuine national development must prioritize early childhood care and education and back same up with a radical career revolution where many of her citizens can be convinced to show interests in choosing their careers in early childhood care and education. Such states can do so through introducing incentives that can motivate their citizens to choose their career in early childhood care and education. Nigeria as a state can provide such incentives like scholarships, bursaries and automatic employment for interested persons who wish to choose their careers at the early childhood care and education level by ensuring that the best candidates are allowed to choose their career in early childhood care and education with a special payment package that can take care of the peculiarities of working at this level of education provided and such payment package can be constitutionally backed up by law. To demonstrate some additional measures of seriousness and commitment, the government of Nigeria must directly participate in providing education at this fundamental and foundational level, must provide the right infrastructure and the right teaching learning environments that can boost of the latest instructional aids in the field of early childhood care and education. Through leading by example, the government of Nigeria can mandate private investors to replicate the standard set by the government, in addition to injecting all the innovative and entrepreneurial ideas and practices the private sector is known for. In this way, competition can be effectively promoted and Nigerians can have real value for their investments and patronage of early childhood care and education.

If Nigeria boosts the interests of her citizens so much that they make their career choices in early childhood care and education, Nigeria can consciously be laying strong and formidable foundations that can trigger developmental revolutions in Nigeria's social, cultural, religious, economic, political, environmental, scientific and technological domains in the near future that can be capable of making Nigeria raise her shoulders to the point of competing with the best in the world on the development index. In fact, luring the right personnel into choosing their careers in early childhood care and education has potentials to produce multiplier effects such as providing Nigeria with a solid base for projecting and predicting her national development plans over a period of time in addition to qualitatively rejigging and re-charting Nigeria's human capital development base.

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